

EDITORIAL

BF.7: The new concern for dental practice?

The year 2022 is about to end but a new variant of the Omicron COVID-19 is making everyone worried. This is known as the BF.7 variant. It is highly infectious having a reproduction rate of 10 to 18.6. Experts suggest that this variant will not affect the Indian population as the people here have hybrid immunity of both the vaccine doses and the exposure to other variants of the COVID-19 virus.

The symptoms of this new BF.7 infection are difficulty in breathing, fever, sore throat, common cold, dry or wet cough, body ache, running nose, fatigue, vomiting, diarrhoea. The infection this highly infectious variant cause is not that severe. A person with good immunity can easily resolve the infection.

The people who are more at risk are people with diabetic people, hypertensive patients, elderly people, infants, patients undergoing chemotherapy etc, where the infection appears to become fatal at times.

The BF.7 variant does not require any special precautions. We need to follow few previously given guidelines like.

1. Always wearing a proper mask in public areas.
2. Make sure you are properly vaccinated (regular and booster).
3. Washing our hands at regular intervals.
4. Stay away from touching eyes, nose and mouth without washing hands.
5. Seek immediate medical attention if you have any of the symptoms.
6. Avoid crowds and keep a physical distance from other people.
7. Use a handkerchief or your elbow every time you sneeze or cough.
8. Avoid close contact with people who are infected with the BF.7 variant

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of India has put forward a list of guidelines last year which is available freely on the internet for the dental practitioners. Thus, make yourself safe by maintaining social distancing and proper sanitisation of your operatory. Keep yourself healthy to fight back the virus which has been a nemesis for mankind for the past two years.

I wish everyone good health and a very happy and safe new year ahead.

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Journal of Orofacial Rehabilitation

Indian Prosthodontic Society West Bengal State Branch

